

The Game of Keys and Queries: Enhancing Parallelism Detection in Classical Chinese Poetry with Symbolic Networks

Maciej Kurzynski¹, Xiaotong Xu², Yu Feng³

¹The Advanced Institute for Global Chinese Studies, Lingnan University, Hong Kong

²Department of Chinese Language and Literature, Peking University

³Department of Chinese, Lingnan University, Hong Kong

Corresponding author: Maciej Kurzynski, maciej.kurzynski@ln.edu.hk

Abstract

This article employs a network-based approach to refine training data and improve automatic detection of parallelism in classical Chinese poetry. Parallelism requires syntactic and semantic alignment between each pair of characters across two poetic lines. We leverage the formal constraints of four-couplet regulated verse, where inner couplets (2nd and 3rd) are typically parallel, to build a network of semantically and syntactically aligned characters. Applying the Louvain method for detecting network communities allows us to filter the training dataset by removing false positive (non-parallel inner) and false negative (parallel outer) examples, based on whether corresponding characters belong to the same community. A SikuBERT model, fine-tuned on this filtered dataset, significantly outperforms general-purpose LLMs like GPT-4o and Moonshot AI. The bespoke model allows us to probe further into the classification process, particularly the self-attention mechanism. Here, the similarity between queries (“questions”) and keys (“answers”) determines the mutual relevance of each pair of tokens in a sequence. Our analysis reveals that in parallel couplets, the classification token [CLS], prepended to each sequence to aggregate information for the final classification, generates a query representation that resonates with the key representations of characters at corresponding positions in both lines. This phenomenon is weaker in non-parallel couplets, suggesting that the model learns to detect parallelism by identifying shared semantic and syntactic features of Chinese characters through such key-query interactions.

Keywords

computational poetics, classical Chinese poetry, parallelism, self-attention, classification

I INTRODUCTION

Parallelism is a rhetorical and structural device in poetry where two elements correspond with each other in terms of syntax, meaning, tone, and rhythm. It has been shown to occur universally across cultures (Plaks [1990], Zhang [2021]). In the Sinophone world, the most widely recognized form of parallelism are the red couplets, known as *fai chun* or *chun lian*, traditionally placed on either side of the doors during Lunar New Year. The most exquisite ones, however, can be found in classical poetry. Consider the following example of a pentasyllabic regulated poem, consisting of four couplets:

- 1 空山新雨后，天气晚来秋。
- 2 明月松间照，清泉石上流。
- 3 竹喧归浣女，莲动下渔舟。
- 4 随意春芳歇，王孙自可留。

*After a fresh rain in the empty mountains, the weather turns autumnal as evening comes.
The bright moon shines between the pines, a clear spring flows over the stones.
The bamboo rustles as washing women return, the lotuses sway as fishing boats descend.
Let the spring flowers fade at will, a noble guest can still remain.*

The poem meets the formal requirements of regulated poetry (律诗), consisting of non-parallel outer couplets (no. 1 and 4) and parallel inner couplets (no. 2 and 3). For example, in the second (parallel) couplet, each character in the first line corresponds syntactically and semantically with a character at the same position in the second line: 明 (“bright”) and 清 (“clear”) are adjectives describing the two nouns: 月 (“moon”) and 泉 (“spring”), while the adverbial phrases: 松间 (“between the pines”) and 石上 (“over the stones”) modify the verbs occurring at the last position: 照 (“to shine”) and 流 (“to flow”). This correspondence creates a balanced and harmonious structure, parallel in both form and meaning.

It can be argued that parallelism is not simply a pre-existing element within the lines of a poem, but something that emerges through the act of reading and interpretation. This can be illustrated with the following couplet from Du Fu’s famous poem, *Spring View* 春望:

感时花溅泪，恨别鸟惊心。
[I am] Moved by the times, [and the] flowers shed tears.
[I am] Distressed by parting, [and the] birds startle my heart.

As shown by Cai [2008], the structural and semantic ambiguity of this couplet allows numerous interpretations. Both lines include two grammatical subjects: the implicit subjects in the initial disyllabic segment (those feeling the times and lamenting separation) and the explicit subjects in the following trisyllabic segment (the flowers shedding tears and the birds startling the heart). If the narrator is understood as the shared subject of both di- and trisyllabic segments, then the couplet can be read as “I feel about this wretched time so badly, that even flowers make me shed tears; I regret separation so much that a bird’s call startles my heart.” On the other hand, if we let the flowers and birds function as sole subjects, then the couplet reads: “Feeling the wretched time, flowers shed tears; Regretting separation, birds are startled in their hearts.” If we combined the characters at the 2nd and 3rd positions into disyllabic words, thus changing the 2+(1+2) rhythm into a (1+2)+2 rhythm, the couplet yields yet another interpretation: “Feeling affected by the seasonal flowers (时花), I shed my tears; Hating to see the straying bird (别鸟), my heart is startled by its call.”

The assessment of parallelism is not always objective and clear-cut. For example, the couplet 积获被山阜，流血丹中原 (“Piled up harvests cover mounds; Flowing blood reddens the Central Plains”) can be considered non-parallel because 丹 (“red”) is an adjective, while 被 (“to cover”) is a verb. However, 丹 can also function as a verb in a causative sense, meaning “to make red.” Under this interpretation, the couplet becomes parallel. Another ambiguous example, 炎光延万里，洪川荡湍濑 (“The scorching light extends for ten thousand miles; The vast rivers toss turbulent rapids”) might be considered non-parallel by some readers, given that 万里 (“ten thousand miles”) and 湍濑 (“rapids”) do not belong to the same semantic category; others might argue, however, that 万里 refers to a vast expanse of space, while 湍濑 refers to an equally vast expanse of water, thus matching each other.

Modern scholars and traditional literati alike have long been fascinated by the problem as to what constitutes a parallel couplet. For example, in the chapter “Parallel Phrasing” in his *Literary Mind and the Carving of Dragons*, Liu Xie (460-522) distinguishes four kinds of couplets: verbal (言对), material (事对), antithetical (反对), and direct (正对) (Liu [2015]). A Japanese scholar monk, Kukai (774-835), proficient in Chinese classical literary criticism, identifies as many as 29 different types of couplets (Kukai [1975]). Wang Li, a prominent modern Chinese linguist, argues that the classification of words—pairing nouns with nouns, verbs with verbs, etc.—is foundational to understanding parallelism (Wang [1979]). Andrew Plaks views parallelism not merely as a stylistic tool but as a fundamental mode of textual organization and argumentation (Plaks [1990]). Zhang Longxi offers a comparative view on parallelism as a mode of reasoning common to all humans (Zhang [2021]). Cai Zong-qi traces the development of parallel patterning in Chinese literature beginning with pre-Qin writings and becoming prominent during the Six Dynasties (Cai [2022]).

The problem of parallelism in Chinese poetry has drawn relatively little attention within the NLP community. Lee et al. apply part-of-speech tagging to detect syntactic parallelism in Tang poetry, confirming established views that the inner couplets in regulated poems are more often syntactically parallel than the outer couplets (Lee et al. [2018]). Few other studies focus on the automatic generation of parallel couplets (Yuan et al. [2019], Chiang et al. [2021], Song [2022], Qu et al. [2022]). Our earlier work (Kurzynski et al. [2024]) experimented with LLM-based methods to detect parallelism in classical Chinese poetry, ranging from character embeddings to commercially available LLMs such as ChatGPT. These and other studies apply machine learning techniques to the generation and analysis of Chinese parallel couplets, pushing the boundaries of how well machine intelligence can replicate this sophisticated form of poetic expression. Beyond the technical challenges, however, we believe that computational studies of parallelism can also shed new light on the broader questions of how meaning is generated through language and how humans perceive, structure, and understand the world through patterns and relationships.

Building on our previous efforts in computational detection of parallel couplets, this article introduces a novel network-based method for refining training datasets. We also benchmark a PRC-based large language model (Moonshot AI), specifically trained on Chinese data, against existing solutions. Finally, we analyze common model errors and leverage our bespoke fine-tuned model to provide new insights into the automatic detection of parallelism.

II DATASETS

In this study, we use two distinct datasets for training/validation and testing. Our test dataset contains 6,125 pentasyllabic couplets divided manually into two classes: parallel (2,139 samples) and non-parallel (3,986 samples). All couplets come from the so-called “Six Dynasties” (222-589), a transformative period in the history of Chinese literature which witnessed the development of parallel poetry, ultimately leading to the elegant, regulated verse of the Tang (618-907) and the following eras.

The training/validation dataset (Figure 1) comprises 568,940 pentasyllabic couplets sourced from regulated poetry (五律) spanning the Tang (618–907), Song (960–1279), Yuan (1279–1368), Ming (1368–1644), and Qing (1644–1912) Dynasties. These couplets have been automatically labeled as “parallel” (284,441 examples) and “non-parallel” (284,499 examples), given that, as mentioned above, regulated poetry imposes strict demands on the poem’s formal structure: inner couplets should be parallel, whereas the outer couplets should be non-parallel.

This initial setting allowed the fine-tuned *SikuBERT* to achieve the F1 score of 0.71 (Kurzynski et al. [2024]). However, as we noted in that earlier study, the dataset contains numerous false positive and false negative examples, since many poets did not adhere to the rigid formal requirements. As the size of the dataset prevents manual verification of each training example, we needed to find other methods to filter our data.

Figure 1. Number of Pentasyllabic Couplets per Dynasty

To further enhance the quality of our training dataset, we resorted to network analysis. We first selected all inner couplets and incrementally built a network of Chinese characters by drawing an edge between characters occurring at corresponding positions in each couplet (Figure 2).

Figure 2. An example of network construction with six couplets. We repeat this process for each pair of characters occurring at corresponding positions. For the sake of clarity, only one edge per couplet is shown in the above figure.

Notice that at this stage, we were not concerned with whether two characters correctly correspond to each other in terms of meaning, grammar, or their function in a verse, i.e., whether a nominally parallel couplet is truly parallel. For example, in Figure 2, the semantic relationship between 夏 (“summer”) and 深 (“deep”/“depth”) is not obvious. At scale, however, such

imperfect pairings are leveled out by the much larger number of correct pairings. Having constructed the network (7,822 nodes), we then kept removing nodes with only one neighbor (degree 1) iteratively until we obtained a network where each node had at least two neighbors, containing 6,716 nodes in total (Figure 3). We then applied the Louvain method to find the best community partition, leading to the following result (Table 1). For each community, we suggest a name, provide the top 10 nodes sorted according to their degree, and list 3 most common pairings.

Community	Top Terms	Top Pairings
Verbs	生 (“to live”), 行 (“to walk”), 流 (“to flow”), 归 (“to return”), 分 (“to divide”), 飞 (“to fly”), 开 (“to open”), 来 (“to come”), 经 (“to pass”), 落 (“to fall”)	来-去 (“to come-to go”), 闻-见 (“to hear-to see”), 归-去 (“to return-to leave”)
History & Geography	汉 (“Han”), 楚 (“Chu”), 周 (“Zhou”), 吴 (Wu”), 越 (“Yue”), 湘 (“Xiang”), 苏 (“Su”), 秦 (“Qin”), 淮 (“Huai”), 胡 (“Hu”)	吴-楚 (“Wu-Chu”), 秦-汉 (“Qin-Han”), 吴-越 (“Wu-Yue”)
Nouns	风 (“wind”), 山 (“mountain”), 云 (“cloud”), 书 (“book”), 花 (“flower”), 天 (“sky”), 江 (“river”), 时 (“time”), 衣 (“clothing”), 歌 (“song”)	风-雨 (“wind-rain”), 山-水 (“mountain-water”), 风-月 (“wind-moon”)
Numbers and Quantities	几 (“several”), 一 (“one”), 群 (“group”), 数 (“number”), 半 (“half”), 诸 (“various”), 尺 (“foot”), 千 (“thousand”), 三 (“three”), 双 (“pair”)	一-千 (“one-thousand”), 一-三 (“one-three”), 万-千 (“ten thousand-thousand”)
Directions and Positions	上 (“up”), 下 (“down”), 中 (“middle”), 里 (“inside”), 前 (“front”), 南 (“south”), 间 (“between”), 边 (“side”), 东 (“east”), 西 (“west”)	外-中 (“outside-center”), 上-中 (“top-center”), 南-北 (“south-north”)
Human Experience	人 (“person”), 香 (“fragrance”), 文 (“script”), 华 (“splendid”), 心 (“heart”), 名 (“name”), 愁 (“sorrow”), 神 (“spirit”), 光 (“light”), 声 (“sound”)	声-影 (“sound-shadow”), 声-色 (“sound-color”), 人-客 (“person-guest”)
Adjectives	清 (“clear”), 长 (“long”), 明 (“bright”), 空 (“empty”), 高 (“high”), 寒 (“cold”), 春 (“spring”), 秋 (“autumn”), 老 (“old”), 深 (“deep”)	白-青 (“white-green”), 新-旧 (“new-old”), 白-黄 (“white-yellow”)
Function Words	无 (“none”), 为 (“for/as”), 相 (“mutual”), 何 (“what/why”), 方 (“only”), 同 (“same”), 不 (“not”), 如 (“like”), 还 (“still”), 真 (“true”)	有-无 (“have-not have”), 无-不 (“none-not”), 如-似 (“similar-alike”)

Table 1. Character communities obtained through the Louvain method applied to the network constructed from characters occurring at corresponding positions in nominally parallel (inner) couplets.

The partition robustness has been confirmed by measuring the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) on 100 runs of the Louvain algorithm, obtaining the average score of 0.81, which indicates high consistency across trials. In the crucial, final step, we used the obtained community assignments to filter the training dataset by removing the likely false positive (inner but non-parallel) and false negative (outer but parallel) couplets. Specifically:

- From the nominally parallel, inner couplets, we have removed all couplets that contained four or more pairs of characters that did *not* belong to the same community, since these couplets were likely non-parallel.

- From the nominally non-parallel, outer couplets, we have removed all couplets that contained three or more pairs of characters that *did* belong to the same community, since these couplets were likely parallel.

As indicated, the requirement for an inner couplet to be removed was stricter than the requirement for an outer couplet to be removed. This is because the inner couplet is less likely to be non-parallel than the outer couplet is likely to be parallel. This procedure led to the removal of more than 50,000 couplets that might have otherwise confused the classifier during training. While the filtered dataset is still likely to contain false examples, this additional cleaning step allowed us to significantly improve the classification accuracy, as shown below.

Figure 3. Symbolic network with 20 representative characters per community. Notice the mobility of verbs as they are dispersed across the graph, unlike other, more close-knit communities.

III METHODS

In our previous work, we developed five classification methods: (1) verb position matching, (2) integrated semantic, syntactic, and word segmentation analysis, (3) difference-based character embeddings, (4) structured examples (inner/outer couplets), and (5) GPT-guided classification, as described below:

- (1) **Verb Position Matching:** This baseline approach identified parallelism by focusing on the syntactic positioning of verbs within couplets. A pre-trained *SikuBERT* model was fine-tuned on labeled data, where each character was annotated as a verb (1) or non-verb (0). During inference, verb alignment at corresponding positions across the two lines was used as the primary criterion for classification.
- (2) **Integrated Semantic, Syntactic, and Word Segmentation Analysis:** This method combined three models: word segmentation, part-of-speech (POS) tagging, and character-to-character semantic matching. Fine-tuned models aligned word boundaries, POS tags, and semantic embeddings between corresponding characters in the couplet, producing a composite score to determine parallelism.
- (3) **Difference-Based Character Embeddings:** Using contextual embeddings generated by *SikuBERT*, this approach computed the differences between corresponding characters' embeddings in parallel lines. A classifier was then trained to distinguish between "parallel differences" and "non-parallel differences," capturing structural and semantic alignment in the embedding space.
- (4) **Structured Examples (Inner/Outer Couplets):** This method leveraged the structural regularity of regulated poetry, where the second and third couplets often exhibit parallelism. Positive examples were extracted from these inner couplets, while the first and fourth (outer) couplets served as non-parallel examples. A fine-tuned *SikuBERT* model then classified test couplets based on this pattern.
- (5) **GPT-Guided Classification:** A few-shot prompting approach was applied to GPT-4o, where examples of parallel and non-parallel couplets, along with their succinct analyses, were provided. GPT-4o was requested to analyze the structural and semantic relationships for each test couplet and make a binary decision regarding its parallelism.

In this article, we verify two new approaches. First, we enhance the **Structured Examples** method by using the training data filtered through network analysis, as explained in the Dataset section. Moreover, we improve the training procedure by calculating the validation loss after every 2,000 batches (or 32,000 examples) and stopping the fine-tuning when the validation loss begins to increase, thus preventing over-fitting.

Second, we have used Kimi, a large language model developed by **Moonshot AI**, a Beijing-based startup founded in March 2023. Introduced in October 2023, Kimi has been dubbed the "Chinese ChatGPT" due to its advanced conversational capabilities. It has been trained on extensive Chinese text data and has received significant investment from major Chinese tech companies, including Alibaba and Tencent. As in the GPT approach, we provided Moonshot AI with two examples (one positive and one negative) in the prompt and then requested it to classify the third couplet. We repeated this procedure for each couplet in the test dataset.

IV RESULTS

The results (Table 2) clearly demonstrate the importance of high-quality fine-tuning data for downstream tasks, as the *SikuBERT* classifier enhanced with symbolic networks approach achieves the best performance, beating even the powerful commercial LLMs.

Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1 (%)
VM (baseline)	76.5	72.3	55.0	62.5
ISSA	72.5	68.2	48.0	56.3
ED	75.9	72.0	53.6	61.4
SE	79.1	69.9	72.7	71.3
SE + SymNet	83.7	74.4	81.1	77.6
GPT-4o (2-shot)	79.0	70.7	68.4	69.5
GPT-4o (10-shot)	79.6	73.7	64.4	68.8
Moonshot AI (v1-8k) (2-shot)	79.1	72.2	65.5	68.7

Table 2. Results of Classification Methods. The methods include Verb Matching (VM), Semantic-Syntactic Integration (ISSA), Embedding Differences (ED), Structured Examples (SE), Structured Examples + Symbolic Networks (SE + SymNet), GPT Evaluation (GPT-4o), and Moonshot AI.

V DISCUSSION

5.1 Error Analysis

Despite extensive training data and alignment techniques like RLHF, general-purpose LLMs remain susceptible to hallucination and probability collapse, where initial output tokens unduly influence subsequent generations. These limitations likely contribute to their inferior performance compared to task-specific fine-tuned models. We analyze some of the most common errors below, including the models’ own reasoning translated into English.

5.1.1. Segmentation Errors

Segmentation errors occur when the model fails to correctly parse sentence boundaries or word groupings, leading to misinterpretation of meaning or structure. Segmentation is particularly important for Chinese, where there are no spaces between words.

秦箏何慷慨，齐瑟和且柔。

How stirring is the Qin zither; How harmonious and soft is the Qi se.

- **GPT-4o:** 秦箏 and 齐瑟 are both ancient musical instruments, and their locations and nouns align. 何 and 和且, while differing in function (何 as an interrogative pronoun and 和且 as a conjunction), both express musical qualities, thus matching. 慷慨 and 柔 describe music characteristics and create a striking contrast.
- **Moonshot AI:** 秦箏 and 齐瑟 correspond as ancient instruments representing Qin and Qi states, respectively. 何 matches 和, where 何 is an interrogative, and 和 is a verb indicating harmony. 慷慨 matches 且柔, with 慷慨 describing intense emotion and 且柔 describing soft tones.

Error Analysis: GPT-4o mistakenly compares 何 with 和且, without realizing that 和 is an adjective (“harmonious”) and 且 is a conjunction (“and”). Likewise, Moonshot AI wrongly merges the characters 且 and 柔 into one word. These forced alignments might result from the

models' attempts to align the rest of the interpretation with the correctly detected parallelism in the initial segment (秦箏 and 齐瑟).

5.1.2. Grammatical Recognition Errors

These errors involve incorrect identification of a word's grammatical role, such as misclassifying verbs as nouns or misinterpreting a phrase's function in a couplet.

行行将复行，去去适西秦。

Step by step, I shall walk again; Onward and onward, heading to West Qin.

- **GPT-4o:** 行行 and 去去 are reduplicated verbs emphasizing continuous action, forming a match. 将复行 and 适西秦 are verb phrases, where 将复行 means preparing to travel again, and 适西秦 means heading to West Qin. Both phrases match syntactically as verbs with complements.
- **Moonshot AI:** 行行 and 去去 are verb reduplications for continuity. 将 and 适 are adverbs. 复行 and 西秦 are noun phrases denoting repeated walking and the destination, West Qin.

Error Analysis: GPT-4o correctly identifies the trisyllabic segments as verb phrases but overlooks their structural differences: 将复行 (adverb + predicate) vs. 适西秦 (verb-object structure). Moonshot AI wrongly labels 复行 as a noun phrase.

5.1.3. Word Order Confusion

These errors occur when the model fails to respect the principle of positional parallelism, leading to misaligned comparisons or interpretations.

父母且不顾，何言子与妻？

If even parents are not cared for, how can one speak of children and wife?

- **GPT-4o:** 父母 and 子与妻 correspond as family members. 且不顾 and 何言 both express negation.
- **Moonshot AI:** 父母 and 子与妻 correspond as elders and younger family members. 且 and 何 do not fully align grammatically but suggest progression (“for now” vs. “how”). 不顾 and 言 contrast in meaning as “neglect” vs. “speak,” forming a juxtaposition.

Error Analysis: Both GPT and Moonshot AI match the first two characters of the first verse with the last three characters of the second verse, failing to respect parallelism in corresponding positions.

5.1.4. Missing Links

These errors occur when the models focus too rigidly on literal correspondence, missing the metaphorical relationships.

四面动清风，朝夜起寒色

On all sides moves the clear breeze; Day and night rises the chill hue.

- **GPT-4o:** 四面 and 朝夜 do not match, as the former is a spatial concept, while the latter is a temporal concept. 动 and 起 are corresponding verbs, but 清风 and 寒色 do not fully match because 清风 refers to a tangible natural phenomenon, while 寒色 is an abstract phenomenon. Overall, the two lines lack full correspondence in their elements.
- **Moonshot AI:** 四面 and 朝夜 are mismatched, as one represents spatial direction and the other, a temporal concept. 动 and 起 are verbs, but 动 suggests the continuation of an action, while 起 suggests the start of one, so their meanings are not fully aligned. 清风 and 寒色 do not correspond in meaning either, as 清风 refers to a refreshing breeze, while 寒色 refers to the coldness of color or feeling.

Error Analysis: Both analyses overlook the flexibility and artistic nuance of classical Chinese poetry, especially in balancing spatial and temporal modifiers, dynamic verbs, and sensory imagery.

5.1.5. *Incorrect interpretations, correct classifications*

The model correctly classifies a couplet despite providing an incorrect reading of a poem.

朝与金张期，暮宿许史家。

In the morning, I meet Jin and Zhang; in the evening, I stay at the home of Xu and Shi.

- **GPT-4o:** 朝 and 暮 are time-related words, representing different times of the day, so they match. 与 and 宿 are not a perfect match, but both represent some kind of action, which is acceptable. 金张 and 许史 are both personal names, and they are compound surnames (famous rich merchant Jin Ridi and the Xu brothers of the Han Dynasty, so they match. Although 期 (appointment) and 家 (home) are different in terms of part of speech and semantics, they can be regarded as a symmetrical effect here as the ending words of the sentence.
- **Moonshot AI:** 朝 is contrasted with 暮, referring to morning and evening respectively; 与 is contrasted with 宿, representing an appointment and lodging respectively; 金张 and 许史 are contrasted, both referring to two families in ancient times; 期 is contrasted with 家 representing an appointment and a place of residence respectively.

Error Analysis: The models correctly identify the parallel relationships in the couplet. However, the analysis of the historical references is wrong. 金张 refers to two individuals: Jin Ridi 金日磾 and Zhang Anshi 张安世, who were prominent officials during the reign of Emperor Xuan of Han (94-48 BC). 许史 also refers to two individuals: Xu Bo 许伯 and Shi Gao 史高, who were relatives of Emperor Xuan through marriage. Rather than a compound surname of one person, each disyllabic segments refers to two distinct individuals.

5.1.6. General comments

A significant issue with LLM-based couplet analysis is the phenomenon of probability collapse in sequence generation. Once the model makes an initial interpretive decision—such as identifying a mismatch or asserting that elements in the first half of a couplet do not align—the subsequent tokens in the analysis are often “pushed” toward interpretations that align with this initial judgment. This behavior stems from the inherent nature of autoregressive models, where each token’s generation is conditioned on the prior context. For instance, if the model determines early on that one component of a couplet is non-parallel, it might disproportionately favor non-parallel interpretations that support this judgment for the remaining tokens, even if alternate readings would have been more accurate. Conversely, if early characters were considered parallel (as in example 5.1.1, where 秦箏 “Qin zither” and 齐瑟 “Qi se” were correctly matched), the following characters might be wrongly segmented to align with the parallel interpretation. This self-reinforcing mechanism limits the model’s ability to independently reassess subsequent elements while keeping previous judgements “under advisement,” and as such may lead to a compounding of errors.

Another important issue lies in tokenization variability, particularly in how GPT-like models tokenize classical Chinese characters. Classical Chinese is highly concise, with each character often representing a standalone morpheme or concept. Ideally, each character should be treated as an atomic unit or part of a larger multi-character entity (such as disyllabic nouns), but in practice tokenization can introduce significant discrepancies into how each individual character is represented. For example, some characters might be assigned a single token, while others might be split into multiple tokens, as shown in the following example (Table 3).

Character	GPT-4o	cl100k_base (GPT 4)	Llama-3-70B
秦	134810	14191, 99	120006
箏	7004, 251	29857, 251	29857, 251
何	13811	99849	99849
慷	20036, 115	162, 227, 115	101557, 115
慨	20036, 101	162, 227, 101	101557, 101
，	979	3922	3922
齐	64846	165, 121, 238	114796
瑟	45283, 253	163, 239, 253	124067
和	5884	34208	34208
且	44966	3574, 242	103786
柔	137529	76475, 242	115289

Table 3. Poetic couplet represented by different tokenizers. Each character is converted into one or more tokens (data obtained from *Tiktokenizer*).

This inconsistent tokenization might introduce difficulties in preserving the integrity of comparisons between characters. When characters are split into multiple tokens, their semantic or grammatical roles are diluted, as attention mechanisms must distribute focus across several tokens rather than a single cohesive unit. This diffusion of attention can obscure relationships between characters and disrupt the model’s ability to accurately assess parallelism, alignment, or poetic harmony. Furthermore, tokenization discrepancies may cause the model to misinterpret word boundaries, grammatical structures, or metaphorical nuances, exacerbating errors in the overall analysis.

5.2. Synchronized Attention

A key advantage of training a bespoke, task-specific model, as opposed to relying on general-purpose, commercial LLMs, is the access to the model’s internal weights and mechanisms. This allows for a deeper understanding of the classification process beyond surface-level performance metrics. In our investigation of the fine-tuned *SikuBERT* model, we discovered a phenomenon of “synchronized attention,” which provides a novel perspective on how the model identifies and interprets parallelism in classical Chinese poetry.

The core of the Transformer architecture is the self-attention mechanism, which enables each token in a sequence to attend to every other token, dynamically weighting their relevance to one another. This process involves three matrix transformations: queries (Q), keys (K), and values (V). Each of these is a learned linear projection, applied to each token’s vector representation passed up from the previous layer. In each attention layer, the query matrix transforms each token’s vector into a “question” representation, effectively encoding what information that token seeks from the sequence. Concurrently, the key matrix transforms each token’s vector into an “answer” representation, indicating the information it offers to other tokens. The interaction between these “questions” and “answers” is quantified through the dot product of the query and key representations, calculated for each pair of tokens. This produces a matrix of scalar values, which are subsequently scaled and converted into probabilities via the *softmax* function. These probabilities (“attention weights”) represent the strength of correspondence between each query and each key: for any two tokens x_i and x_j , the attention weight signifies how much of the “question” $Q(x_i)$ is answered by $K(x_j)$. For instance, in a well-trained model, the character 风 (“wind”), transformed through its query vector, might ask: “I am looking for nouns related to nature. Which tokens represent such nouns?” Its dot product with the key representation of 水 (“water”) should be thus significantly larger than with that of 有 (“to have”), reflecting their respective semantic relatedness and unrelatedness to the query.

The intricate interplay of queries and keys within the attention mechanism suggests a new interpretation of poetic parallelism, namely, two lines are parallel if the characters occupying corresponding positions in both lines effectively “answer” the same underlying “question.”

Figure 4. Simplified visualization of BERT architecture.

In BERT-based models, a special classification token, denoted as [CLS], is prepended to the input sequence (Figure 4). During the encoding process, the [CLS] token participates in the self-attention mechanism like any other token, both attending to and receiving attention from

other tokens in the sequence. However, a critical divergence occurs in the final layer. Here, having aggregated information from the entire sequence through successive layers of self-attention, the [CLS] token’s vector representation passes through a classifier which outputs the probability distribution over the target classes. In our case of binary classification, the model outputs probabilities for two classes: parallel (1) and non-parallel (0).

We hypothesized that, in the final layer, the [CLS] token’s query vector should formulate “questions” that effectively probe the presence or absence of parallel relationships between the two lines of a couplet. In other words, for a parallel couplet, the corresponding characters in both lines should provide similar “answers” to the “question” posed by the [CLS] token.

To investigate this, we examined the attention patterns in the final layer of our fine-tuned *SikuBERT* model. Each input sequence comprises 13 tokens: the [CLS] token, five tokens for the first line, a comma, five tokens for the second line, and the end-of-sequence [SEP] token. The model’s architecture incorporates 12 attention heads in each layer. Within each head in the final layer, we measured the strength of correspondence (“attention weights”) between the query representation of the [CLS] token, or Q([CLS]), and the key representations of all other tokens in the sequence, including itself, effectively quantifying how much each token “answers” the [CLS] token’s “question.” The results can be visualized as attention heatmaps (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Attention distribution for [CLS] token in parallel (left) and non-parallel (right) couplets, the top layer of the fine-tuned *SikuBERT*. The color scale has been computed for entire heatmaps. Notice that heads 2, 5, 7, and 11 tend to focus on the [CLS] token itself rather than other elements in the sequence, which might be a way for [CLS] token to preserve its own information rather than being completely replaced by values from other tokens.

In the parallel couplet (Figure 5, left), the attention distribution from the [CLS] token to the first line (明月松间照) closely mirrors that to the second line (清泉石上流) across most attention heads. This indicates that corresponding characters in the two lines are providing similar “answers” to the [CLS] token’s query. This pattern is significantly less pronounced in the non-parallel couplet (Figure 5, right).

To quantify this “synchronized attention” phenomenon, we computed the Pearson correlation coefficient between the attention scores from the [CLS] token to the five characters in the first line and the scores from the [CLS] token to the five characters in the second line, for both

parallel and non-parallel couplets. This correlation measures the degree to which an increase in attention to a character in the first line corresponds to an increase in attention to the character at the same position in the second line. We calculated these correlations for each attention head in the final layer, using all examples from our held-out test dataset. The average correlation coefficients are visualized in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Average Pearson’s correlation coefficients on attention distributions for the five characters in both lines in parallel and non-parallel couplets, layer 12.

Parallel couplets exhibit significantly higher average correlation coefficients across all attention heads compared to non-parallel couplets. This strongly supports our hypothesis: in parallel couplets, matching characters are responding similarly to the same “question” posed by the [CLS] token in the final layer, while this consistent response pattern is much weaker in non-parallel couplets. This demonstrates that the model has learned to leverage the key-query interactions within the attention mechanism to discern the nuanced relationships that constitute parallelism in classical Chinese poetry. The different attention heads, each specializing in capturing different aspects of these relationships (syntactic, semantic, grammatical), collectively contribute to the model’s ability to accurately identify parallel structures.

VI CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced a novel, network-driven approach to significantly enhance the accuracy of parallelism detection in classical Chinese poetry. By constructing a symbolic network of Chinese characters based on their co-occurrence patterns within parallel couplets in regulated verse (律詩) and employing the Louvain algorithm to identify character communities, we were able to refine our training dataset by filtering out potentially misleading examples. This community-based filtering, which leverages the established structural norms of regulated poetry, led to a substantial improvement in classification performance. Moreover, we discovered a previously undocumented phenomenon, which we call “synchronized attention,” where corresponding characters in parallel lines elicit similar attention scores from the model’s classification token, highlighting how the model leverages key-query interactions to identify parallel structures.

These results underscore the critical importance of high-quality, task-specific training data for achieving optimal performance in complex computational linguistics tasks, particularly within specialized domains like classical Chinese poetry. Our project contributes to a deeper understanding of both the intricacies of classical Chinese poetry and the capabilities and limitations of current AI models in analyzing complex literary phenomena.

LIMITATIONS

While this study demonstrates a significant improvement in parallelism detection through network-guided data refinement, it is not without limitations. Firstly, our method relies on the assumption that character communities identified through co-occurrence in nominally parallel couplets accurately reflect semantic and syntactic relationships. While the Louvain algorithm provided consistent and interpretable communities, some nuances might be lost in the broad categorization of characters, potentially leading to the removal of valid parallel couplets and retention of problematic ones. Furthermore, our filtering approach, although effective, is based on a simple threshold of community mismatches within couplets. More sophisticated metrics for evaluating the degree of parallelism, perhaps incorporating semantic similarity or syntactic alignment, could lead to more nuanced data refinement.

Another limitation stems from the fact that our dataset primarily consists of pentasyllabic regulated poetry. The generalizability of our approach to other poetic forms or styles may need further investigation.

Finally, our current model, despite its strong performance, still fundamentally operates on a character-to-character matching paradigm. While effective, further improvements in accuracy might necessitate moving beyond this granular level to consider the significance of polysyllabic terms and phrases, as pairs like 北海 (the northern sea, adjective + noun) and 江南 (Yangtze's south, noun + adjective or noun + noun) exhibit parallelism on a higher semantic level that is not captured by individual character analysis. Incorporating mechanisms to recognize and evaluate parallelism at the poly-syllabic scale could unlock a deeper understanding of more complex poetic structures.

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